

The Influence of Employee Competence on Employee Performance in The Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community of Binjai City

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of competency on employee performance at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Office. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with a total of 61 people. The results of the analysis show that competency has a significant influence on employee performance (T-statistic 2,924 > 1.670; P-value 0.005 < 0.05), which indicates that increasing competency directly increases employee performance. The result of the Adjusted R Square value is 0.112 or 11.20%, which means that employee competency has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 88.80% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. This finding provides insight into the relationship between competency and performance, emphasizing the importance of competency in improving employee performance.

Keywords: competence; employee performance, women's empowerment.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations will develop and be able to survive in a competitive environment if they are supported by employees who are competent in their fields. Employee competencies consisting of knowledge, abilities/skills, attitudes are adjusted to the field of work required by the organization, so that it can produce high-achieving employee performance.

Employee performance is basically a description of the employee's ability to handle each job, where the level of employee performance can be assessed from the employee's ability to produce work that meets predetermined standards. Meanwhile, low employee performance is caused by several factors such as: indiscipline at work, late completion of tasks and low responsibility for work, so that the work results obtained are not optimal, because they do not meet the expected standards/targets, resulting in low performance. employees will influence the quality of service to the community. Therefore, it is expected that every employee has competence.

Competency is a person's characteristics that are related to effective and/or superior performance in certain work situations (Rahmat & Basalamah, 2019). Competence is said to be a basic characteristic because individual characteristics are a deep and inherent part of a person's personality that can be used. to predict various specific job situations.

This is because competence is the ability to carry out or carry out a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and is supported by the work attitude required by the job. Thus, competency shows skills and knowledge that are characterized by professionalism in a particular field as the most important or superior in that field.

The phenomenon seen in the Department of Village Community Empowerment, Women and Child Protection in Binjai City in improving the performance of women's empowerment is not as expected, this is proven by the problems that occur in the field, namely low employee competence seen from the behavior of employees who are irresponsible and work, such as many employees arriving late, good attendance but not carrying out their work optimally, completing work not on time and providing unsatisfactory service.

Many factors can influence employee performance in empowering women. In this study the researcher limited the Competency variable with Training as an intervening variable. Competency is a person's characteristics that are related to effective and/or superior performance in certain work situations (Rahmat & Basalamah, 2019).

Meanwhile, according to another opinion, employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been determined or that apply within the organization (Mangkunegara, 2016).

To measure competency in this research, it refers to the indicators set by Rahmat in (Rahmat & Basalamah, 2019), which include:

- 1) A motive is something a person consistently thinks or desires that causes an action.
- 2) Traits are physical characteristics and consistent responses to situations or information.
- 3) Self-concept is a person's attitudes, values, or self-image.
- 4) Knowledge is the information that people have in a specific field.
- 5) Skills are the ability to perform certain physical or mental tasks.

Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements (Fahmi, 2017). Meanwhile, according to another opinion, employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been determined or that apply within the organization (Mangkunegara, 2016).

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

- 1) Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
- 2) Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.
- 3) Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
- 4) Cooperate with other people at work.

The aim of this research is to investigate the influence of competence on the performance of empowering women employees at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City. It is hoped that the results of this research can provide a deeper understanding of the factors that influence employee performance at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community (DP3AM) Service, as well as the potential implications for performance and competency. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The type of research that will be used is quantitative associative, namely research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2018b). In this research, the exogenous variable is Competence (X). Meanwhile, the endogenous variable is Employee Performance (Y). This research was carried out from May 2024 to June 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) of Binjai City, totaling 61 people.

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique when all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 61 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

- X = Employee Competency
- a = Constant
- b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Employee Competence (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. This coefficient of determination test was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest scores, rating scores and standard deviations for each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Competence	61	3.00	5.00	4.1607	,60643
Performance	61	2.00	5.00	4.2131	,83521
Valid N (listwise)	61				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess employee competency and employee performance at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) as above average, with mean values of 4,160 and 4,213 respectively on a 1- 5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.606 for employee competency and 0.835 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Competency Variable Validity Test Results (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KOM1	0.804 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM2	0.788 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM3	0.791 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM4	0.737 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM5	0.844 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the Employee Competency variable have a correlation coefficient of > 0.252 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Employee Competency variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a)

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.758 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.808 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.803 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.852 > 0.252	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on employee performance variables have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.252 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for employee performance variables are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Employee Competency	0.841	5
Employee Performance	0.816	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the Employee Competency and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2,175	,704		3,087	,003
	Competence	,490	,168	,356	2,924	,005

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 2.175 + 0.490X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 2.175 means that if there is no employee competency, then there is an employee performance of 2.175 points. The Employee Competency regression coefficient is 0.490, meaning that Employee Competency influences an increase in employee performance by 0.490 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,356a	,127	,112	,78716

a. Predictors: (Constant), Competence

The test results in table 7 show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.112 or 11.20%, which means that employee competency has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 88.80% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of employee competency on employee performance at the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Department of Binjai City

Ha: There is an influence of employee competency on employee performance at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	2,175	,704			3,087	,003
Competence	,490	,168	,356		2,924	,005

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $2.924 > t$ table 1.670, with a significance value of $0.005 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between employee competency on employee performance at the Women's Empowerment Service. , Protection of Children and the Community of Binjai City.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Competency on Performance, it shows that Competency has an influence on Performance. The implications of these findings indicate that increasing capabilities that focus on empowerment alone is not enough to improve employee performance. Workplace organizations need to explore other factors that are more effective in improving employee performance through empowering women. Office management must understand that empowerment alone is not enough and needs to be combined with other strategies that are more personal and directly touch employees so that it is easy to increase competency. By improving Training, organizations can strengthen the positive impact of Competencies, which in turn can increase employee performance, creativity and commitment.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Affairs in Binjai City. This can be seen from the T-statistic value of $2.924 > 1.670$ with a P-Value value of $0.011 < 0.05$. This means that if competency is increased, employee performance will increase.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.112 or 11.20%, which means that employee competency has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 88.80% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the research results, discussions and conclusions obtained, suggestions that can be given are, Based on the research results, it is known that the Competency variable needs to be maintained and improved. Therefore, the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) should increase training for employees. The training provided must also be more diverse because with diverse training it will be possible to broaden the competence of employees as well as increase knowledge. For example, holding time management training improves service. It is hoped that these steps can further improve employee competency, thereby increasing knowledge and also improving employee performance.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12683699>

Business Students in Batam City Indonesia. *Journal of Archives of Business Research*, 7(6), 33–43.